

Interactive Methods Of Spiritual And Moral Education Of Young People In The Process Of Learning Foreign Languages

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with the use of interactive methods to develop moral and spiritual education of youth in the process of learning foreign languages. Through teaching the English language teachers are trying to develop not only professional skills but also to promote the growth of spiritual and moral values among university students. In the process of acquiring English language interactive methods enable students learn critical thinking, self-confidence, respect to others, honesty, solving to problems, empathy, self-esteem and good manners.

Keywords: Students, education, spiritual education, method, interactive method, learner, foreign language, university, role-play, activity, approach.

INTRODUCTION.

As it is known that English is used globally for economic, political and educational purposes, the demand of teaching and learning English language has risen up considerably in recent years. Today, knowing a foreign language offers a great deal of opportunities for every specialist and in each sphere of activities. Teaching is a process of not only giving information and accounting for how to use the language itself but also integrating moral and spiritual education into the teaching process. From the first day of Independence Day, upbringing of a harmonious and healthy generation has become a priority. Because of the fact that the destiny of the younger generation is measured by its spiritual maturity, issues of spiritual education are always relevant in the education system. Our first President Islam Karimov writes: Spirituality is a force that encourages spiritual purification and ascension, enriches a person's inner world, strengthens his

faith, and awakens his conscience. Education in Uzbekistan emphasizes the approach which combines intellectual aspects with moral and spiritual upbringing of learners. In particular, universities are trying hard to develop not only professional competences, students' spiritual interests, constructive and creative capability and readiness for lifelong learning and self-development. The process of globalization and modernization of higher education requires the future specialists modern educational tools and new pedagogical approaches, the development of multifarious competences cultural, professional and social. At the same time, it is inevitable that the formation of personal values, the improvement of students' moral and spiritual education is closely related to professional growth. Farabi mentions, in the spiritual development of man: in the acquisition of knowledge, experience – an essential place belongs to teaching the basics of science. In the

course of training, it is vital to create conditions for the development of intelligence, since the development of the foundations of scientific knowledge accelerates the cognitive process, spiritual growth of a young man. The effectiveness of spiritual growth depends to some extent on teaching methods, on the skill of the teacher.

METHODOLOGY

Recent and emerging technological advances make it possible to develop interactive learning environments to support new ways of learning. In most universities, teachers and students have discovered the limitations of the traditional methods, such as lecture, explanation, exercise, etc. However, as these are considered as the basis for professional growth, it is impossible to deny them completely.

Therefore, it happens the need for new methodological approaches where the students can perform independent activities and work in a comfortable rhythm. Innovative methods in foreign language teaching are increasingly moving towards learner centered approaches. In these, learning becomes an active process of discovery and participation based on self-motivation rather than on more passive acquaintance of facts and rules (Sfard, 1998). Interactive teaching strategies help to create the interaction among students and training/development of key social personality traits.

Through the interactive methods, students learn to solve problematic situations, to analyze and correspond information logically and critically, to think different opinions, to make well-developed decisions, to take part in discussions, to collaborate with different people. Students participate in various kinds of activities at foreign language classes that is individual, pair, group and team.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is important to point out that interactive methods not only enable students

acquire knowledge and communicative skills in a foreign language but also help to form moral and spiritual qualities as follows:

- Reflection on one's own emotions;
- Self-confidence;
- Respect to others;
- Self-control;
- Empathy;
- Recognition of relationship;
- Humanism;
- Peace-loving;
- Justice;
- Honesty;
- Good manners, etc.

Among the most well-known forms of interactive methods, the following kinds should be mentioned: brainstorming, case study, debate, discussions, dialogue, games, analysis of situations, SWOT Analysis, projects, role plays, presentation and others. Role play is one of the most popular activity in foreign language teaching. It helps to motivate and activate the class. It can be adapted for students of any age group or language level. Learners are involved in a situation which requires communication. Even a student who is shy or reluctant to speak cannot avoid participating with enthusiasm. Role play enables a learner to unfold his potential and proceed towards socialization and more independence. While playing in groups, a student will learn rules and regulations with the appropriate set of moral values. They can gain some values and qualities, that is sharing, cooperation, respecting and accepting others, learning from others, developing a positive, realistic self-concept, accepting and demonstrating empathy, accepting challenge, feeling pride in accomplishment, enjoying living and learning. Furthermore, instruments will have a positive effect to the process of teaching if they are utilized in a proper way and efficiently by a teacher. The effective application of instruments following

tape recorders, interactive whiteboards, projectors, visual aids, books, a variety of multimedia equipment allows to gain new information, listen to texts and provide the development of speech and other skills.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, interactive methods are the most important and beneficial tools to the development of moral and spiritual education of youth in the process of foreign language learning. Because of that, today's teachers should familiarize with the profitable sides of this method and contribute to the quality of education, delivery of teaching material and effectiveness of learning as much as possible.

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